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Reading of Books and Newspapers in the Italian Regions Between 2005 and 2022

Between 2005 and 2022 the value decreased by -17.42%

Istat calculates the reading of books and newspapers. The variable is calculated as the percentage of people aged 6 and over who have read at least four books a year - paperbacks, e-books, online books, audiobooks - for reasons not strictly scholastic or professional and/or have read newspapers - paper and/or online - at least three times a week for all people aged 6 years and over. The data is collected as part of the Survey on Aspects of Daily Life. The data refers to the period between 2005 and 2022 for all Italian regions and macro-regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions for reading of books and newspapers in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for the value of reading books and newspapers in the Italian regions with a value of 54.9, followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 47.9 units and from Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 45.5 units. In the middle of the table are Liguria with a value of 39.5 units, followed by Tuscany with a value of 39.4 and Lazio with a value of 36.4 units. Campania closes the ranking with a value of 22.7 units, followed by Basilicata with a value of 22.6 units and Sicily with a value of 21.2 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in reading of books and newspapers between 2005 and 2022. Piedmont is in first place by value of the percentage change in reading of books and newspapers between 2005 and 2022 with a change from an amount of 28.3 units up to 32.3 units or equal to +14.13%. Puglia is in second place with a variation from an amount of 25 units up to 23.4 units or equal to -1.6 units equal to -6.4%. Abruzzo follows with a variation from an amount of 34.8 units up to 32.3 units or equal to -2.5 units equal to -7.18%. In the middle of the table are the Marche with a value equal to -15.79% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 41.8 units in 2005 up to a value of 40.5 units in 2022. Piedmont follows with a variation of -15.8% equal to a variation from an amount of 48.1 units up to a value of 40.5 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a value equal to -15.87% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 52.3 units up to a value of 44 units equal to a value of -8.3 units. Lazio closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -26.02% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 49.2 units up to a value of 36.4 units, followed by Umbria with a variation equal to -26.1% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 43.3 units up to a value of 32 units, and finally Liguria with a variation equal to -31.06% corresponding to a variation to an amount of 57.3 units up to a value of 39.5 units equal to a value of -17.8 units. Between 2005 and 2022 on average the value of the average variation in the Italian regions went from an amount of 43.62 units up to a value of 36.02 units or equal to an amount of -7.60 units equal to -17,42%.

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Ranking of the macro-regions by percentage change in reading of books and newspapers between 2005 and 2022. The South is in first place for the value of the percentage change between 2005 and 2022 equal to a value of -8.37% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 26.30 units up to a value of 24.10 units. Southern Italy is in second place among the Italian macro-regions for the value of the percentage change in reading books and newspapers between 2005 and 2022, equal to a change from an amount of 28.50 units up to 24.80 units equal to -12.98%. The North-East follows with a variation equal to -14.81% corresponding to a variation between an amount of 52.00 units up to 44.30 units or equal to an amount of -7.70 units. Below is the North with a value equal to -17.46% corresponding to a variation between 52.70 units up to a value of 43.50 units. The North-West follows with -19.36% corresponding to 53.20 units up to 42.90 units. The value of reading books and newspapers in the Islands decreased by an amount equal to -20.78% equivalent to a value from 33.20 units to 26.30 units. The value of reading books and newspapers in Central Italy decreased by -24.69% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 49.00 units to 36.90 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we propose a clustering with a k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two different cluster structures are identified:

- Cluster 1: Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Liguria, Sardinia, Valle d'Aosta, Tuscany, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Piedmont, Trentino, Lazio, Marche, Umbria;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Molise, Abruzzo.

Considering the average value of reading books and newspapers in the Italian regions we can see that Cluster 1 is dominant compared to Cluster 2. We can see that the regions that are part of Cluster 1 are all in the Centre-North, while the regions in Cluster 2 is part of the South. There is therefore a clear distinction between Central-Northern and Southern Italy in the sense of reading books and newspapers. The North-South divide is also represented in access to reading books and newspapers. However, we note, by plotting the average of Cluster 1 against Cluster 2 that both show a decreasing trend between 2005 and 2022. The following considerations arise from this:

- There is a gap between Northern and Southern Italy in terms of reading books and newspapers
- Both Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 show a decreasing trend between 2005 and 2022.

Conclusions. The value of reading newspapers and newspapers decreased by 17.42% between 2005 and 2022 in the Italian regions. It is likely that the use of social networks such as Facebook, Instagram, Tik Tok and LinkedIn have reduced the attention of many readers towards books and newspapers. To this trend we must also add that the world of online video games, together with video streaming platforms such as Youtube, Netflix, Amazon Prime which may have offered valid alternatives to publishing understood as entertainment. However, it is very likely that the publishing world has also lost the opportunity to access high levels of digitalisation and technological innovation, seizing new business opportunities.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Years	Piemonte	Valle d'Aosta	Liguria	Lombardia	Trentino-Alto Adige	Veneto	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	Emilia-Romagna	Toscana	Umbria
2005	48,1	58,2	57,3	54,9	64,9	47,9	56,3	52,3	53,2	43,3
2006	46,5	59	57,4	53,9	65	49,4	56,5	56,3	51,5	41,3
2007	50	56,1	53,8	54,1	66,1	50,4	60,2	54,5	54,7	41,8
2008	48,7	58	57,6	52,6	65,2	48,8	60,4	53,3	50,1	42,7
2009	52,1	52,3	56,6	51,8	66,2	48,8	59,6	52,9	50,3	39,5
2010	49,3	54,6	54,1	52	65,4	52,2	57,7	53,5	53,4	39,8
2011	50	52	52	51,7	63,2	51	58,7	50,7	51,3	38,8
2012	46,2	55,5	50,7	50	62,5	50,8	56,6	51,8	47,4	38
2013	44,8	50,6	48,5	48,1	57,9	47,2	57,1	48,1	44,7	35,1
2014	44,6	49,3	47,3	44,3	59,9	42,8	57,6	49	44,3	36,5
2015	44,1	51,6	48,3	46,2	60,3	42,8	56,1	46,8	47,5	41,9
2016	45,2	54,8	49,3	48,6	60,3	47,6	58,7	50	47,2	41
2017	41,2	47,3	50,2	45	58	46,5	55,1	49,1	43	36,8
2018	45,1	49,1	50,2	47	56,2	45	53	49,9	47,5	35,4
2019	42,8	49	44,2	44,7	57,2	46,5	52	45,8	44,7	36,6
2020	42,3	49,8	48,3	46,4	57,2	44,6	52,6	49,4	40,5	37,8
2021	42,1	47,5	43,7	43,8	55,5	40,2	49,4	42,9	41,5	35,8
2022	40,5	45,5	39,5	44,4	54,9	41,5	47,9	44	39,4	32
Years	Marche	Lazio	Abruzzo	Molise	Campania	Puglia	Basilicata	Calabria	Sicilia	Sardegna

2005	41,8	49,2	34,8	28,3	24,5	25	25,1	28,9	27,1	51,3
2006	42,7	46,3	33,2	28,9	26,6	31,1	28,5	26,7	28,2	52
2007	42,9	46,7	34,1	30,7	26	26,6	27,4	25	27,6	51,5
2008	40,7	48,4	35,5	28,8	24,9	24,5	26,6	26,6	28,1	52,7
2009	43,3	46	38,8	30,8	28,7	29,3	25,6	29,4	29,3	55,7
2010	41,6	47,8	36,2	29,3	27,1	30,4	26,1	29	28,7	55,9
2011	39,4	44,9	37,1	28,1	25,6	27,4	25,1	26	25,6	57,8
2012	40,2	43,2	38,4	26,7	22,1	26,9	24,9	28,3	26,1	49,8
2013	39,3	39,4	32,4	27	21	23,8	23	23,1	21,9	50,2
2014	37,3	40,5	31,4	29,1	21,2	24,1	20,8	23,3	21,7	49,9
2015	38,5	37,5	29,9	25,4	21,1	23,6	21,9	21	25,4	49,1
2016	40,7	42,6	36,8	31,4	23,8	26,8	24,4	21,5	26,1	51,5
2017	38,7	40,1	31,8	29,4	20,6	24	23,9	21,5	23,1	48,2
2018	39,6	38,5	31,7	31	21,4	25,3	27,1	22,1	24,1	48,3
2019	39	39,1	35,5	27,9	21,4	26,4	24,3	23,8	24,2	45
2020	34,8	39,6	33,8	27,7	21,7	25,5	23,6	20,1	26,2	44,5
2021	34,8	39,7	32,1	27,8	22,3	24,6	22,6	22,7	23,9	45
2022	35,2	36,4	32,3	32,3	22,7	23,4	22,6	23	21,2	41,7

